

On the Road Again. Next Stop: Sustainability

A Qualitative Multi-Case Study on Logistic Service Providers in Europe

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Bachelor's Degree Thesis 15 HE Credits
Subject: Business Administration
Spring semester 2020
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Acknowledgements

We would like to thank our supervisor Christoph Baldauf for his support during the writing process. Secondly, we owe special thanks to the interviewees of this study for participating under aggravated circumstances due to the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. It has been an interesting time writing a thesis during a global pandemic and we are grateful for being held safe by the university. Moreover, we would like to thank the following for their invaluable support and encouragement throughout the researching and writing process: Sonja Behrens and Anders Lennartsson. Lastly, we would like to acknowledge and appreciate the teamwork that went into this research without which this paper would not have been possible in the first place.

Abstract

Purpose – Awareness of environmental sustainability is steadily growing in Europe and one industry that has particular difficulties defending current business operations is the logistics sector. The purpose of this paper is to comprehend the process behind implementing environmental sustainability into the daily practices of a Logistics Service Provider (LSP), to evaluate future possibilities of such implementations and to identify the drivers and barriers to this process.

Design/methodology/approach – This qualitative multi-case study was conducted using semi-structured interviews and public, Corporate Social Responsibility-related (CSR) material.

Findings – Customers have immense influence over LSPs business practices including sustainability. However, for now, cost-effectiveness appears to be more of a priority compared to green logistics for their customers. Governmental regulations act as functioning, but not necessarily, welcomed driver to sustainability. LSPs are mostly reactive in the implementation of green initiatives but have so far shown a good track record on the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) steps to sustainability.

Research limitations/implications – Limitations of this study include the sample size of four companies and the confined external validity given the qualitative nature of this paper. Further statistical support is needed to support and reinforce the findings and generalise outside the given sample.

Practical implications – Findings from this study may be used to inform LSPs about possible ways they could incorporate and implement environmental sustainability measures into their daily business operations.

Originality/value – Previous research has mostly focused on small and medium-sized LSPs in a specific country. The theoretical framework of the triple bottom line model is not yet fully communicated in the sector; a gap addressed by investigating the implementation process of the TBL strategy in multinational LSPs headquartered in Europe.

Keywords – Operations Management, Sustainability, Logistics, LSPs, Triple Bottom Line, Multi-case study

Paper type – Bachelor Thesis

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List of Abbreviations

3PL / 3PLs	Third-party Logistics Provider(s)
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
EUR	Euro currency
ESG	Environmental, Social and Governance
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
IPCC	International Panel on Climate Change
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCL	Less than Container Load
LSP / LSPs	Logistics Service Provider(s)
NGO	Non-governmental Organisation
OEM / OEMs	Original Equipment Manufacturer(s)
R&D	Research and Development
ROI	Return on Investment
ROA	Return on Asset
SDG / SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
STM	Sustainable Transportation Model
TBL	Triple Bottom Line
USD	United States Dollar

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

It is common ground that today's focus on sustainability has reached an unprecedented scale actively affecting society and operating businesses alike; a consensus reached by decision-makers on an international level (McKinnon, 2015). The logistics sector is just one of the fields that have been impacted by this change and indeed one of the main actors regarding environmental issues in light of globalization and, consequently, increasing demand in consumerism (European Commission, 2011). As the size of the freight forwarding market grew to over 150bn EUR worldwide in 2018 (Statista, 2020a) and more than 180 thousand containers were shipped that year each day on sea freight alone (Statista, 2020b) it thus comes to no surprise that civil society and government policies are applying pressure to the logistics sector; a mere reflection of the global demand for significant changes needed towards greener ways of managing emissions and resources on a global scale (Centobelli, Cerchione & Esposito, 2017). Inevitably, the question then quickly shifts to the ways business goals and priorities can be altered to successfully reflect their focus on sustainability through the application of green initiatives and environmental regulations; a fine balance whose code is yet to be cracked (Oberhofer & Dieplinger, 2014). Yet in a competitive and highly demanding field such as the logistics sector, the transition towards an overall greener approach of conducting business has been far from organic for a variety of reasons. Firstly, an adjustment period towards these new regulations is vital to be accounted for (Battini, Persona & Sgarbossa, 2014); while academics are talking about sustainability in the logistics sector more frequently since the 1990s (McKinnon, 2015), regulations in many countries were not established before the 2010s and large logistics firms introduced sustainability tracking just recently (Piecyk & Björklund, 2015). Moreover, considering that there is no 'one fits all' model, room for trial and error is needed taking into account the relatively new approach (Lane, 2019). Further, such a large-scale adaptation entails a great deal of internal change both horizontally and vertically (Yang, Lu, Haider & Marlow, 2013). Last, but certainly not least, the above factors are highly dependent on the resources and the priorities of the respective businesses in question; thus transforming the issue into a much more multifaceted one (Colicchia, Marchet, Melacini & Perotti, 2013; Evangelista, 2014; Lieb & Lieb, 2010).

In an attempt to assess sustainability, scholars have used a holistic approach accounting for economic, environmental and social issues (Centobelli et al., 2017; Lane, 2019; Lee & Wu,

2014; Shi, Arthanari, Liu & Yang, 2019; Smokers, Tavasszy, Chen & Guis, 2014). Described by Elkington (1997) as the Triple Bottom Line (TBL), this approach stresses the importance of interconnectedness among these three dimensions and the necessity to evaluate businesses not just on a financial but also on an environmental and social bottom line. Despite calls for an investigation of the whole supply chain, for instance through Life Cycle Assessments (LCA) (Battini et al., 2014; Maas, Schuster & Hartmann, 2014), most scholars within the field have focused on Logistic Service Providers (LSPs) and Third-party Logistic Providers (3PLs) in particular¹. The complexity and recency of the topic have led researchers to decide to take a look at the individual parts of the supply chain and individual parts of sustainability before assessing the entire picture. Additionally, through the close ties LSPs have with manufacturers and customers LSPs' role in the market and the pursuit of sustainability becomes undeniable (Smokers et al., 2014; Maas et al., 2014). Yet these very relations may act as drivers or barriers to accomplish that goal (Evangelista, 2014; Lieb & Lieb, 2010; Colicchia et al., 2013). On the other hand, it has also been shown that becoming environmentally conscious can improve competitiveness (Yang et al., 2013) as well as the industry's image (Lieb & Lieb, 2010). Overall, though, companies implement a diverse set of green strategies resulting in additional differences in performance (Isaksson & Hüge-Brodin, 2013; Laari, Solakivi, Töyli & Ojala, 2016).

Looking at the inter-organization affiliations of firms (Colicchia et al., 2013) can thus reveal relations between the sustainability dimensions and their performance. While the link between sustainable efforts and environmental performance appear to be positive (Laari, Töyli & Ojala, 2018) the effects of such practices on the financial and operational measures are not as clear (Laari et al., 2016). The logistics sector is still heavily shaped by price competition and therefore forces companies to consider environmental sustainability only if it is, in fact, cost-efficient (Smokers et al., 2014). This confirms that sustainability is an important part of the decision-making process nonetheless (Greschner Farkavcova, Rieckhof & Guenther, 2018; Lee & Wu, 2014) and that further research is needed to better understand the relations between the bottom lines and the respective industry actors involved.

¹ Here and in the following *LSPs* will be used as an umbrella term that includes 1PLs (shipper of the consignee), 2PLs (asset-based carriers), 3PLs (provider of outsourced logistics services/supply chain operations) and 4PLs (non-asset based; consulting on logistics services) (Saglietto, 2013).

1.2 Problematisation

As observed from the literature, several studies so far have been conducted regarding the relations within the TBL model. The concluding findings are primarily focused on the nature of those respective relations and their impact on one another; either by supporting the goal of sustainability or acting as an obstacle against it. What has been missing, however, is a closer look at the incorporation of environmental sustainability into LSPs' operations whilst attempting to avoid conflict between the bottom lines and conflict with outside actors which is the main reason we decided to delve deeper into the topic. It has further been shown that environmental sustainability only recently became popular for LSPs to address which makes it all the more relevant to study; especially considering that today's world is in constant change. In 1997, Elkington predicted a particularly fierce conflict between economic and environmental sustainability and despite positive results in terms of rethinking reported by academics since then the industry still seems to be dominated by financial over environmental thinking (Oberhofer & Dieplinger, 2014). Few attempts have been made by previous scholars to address the internal and external ways in which this sector makes business strategies intertwine with sustainability goals and those studies were restricted to specific countries. Scholars, therefore, advised future research to unravel the role of sustainability in the logistics sector either by looking at different geographical regions or by addressing the relation in an even narrower sense (Abbasi & Nilsson, 2016; Evangelista, 2014; Oberhofer & Dieplinger, 2014; Laari et al., 2016; Laari et al., 2018; Lee & Wu, 2014). With that in mind, we conclude that a qualitative multi-case study of multinational LSPs headquartered in Europe would be most appropriate as will be further explained.

Consequently, the underlying research question for this paper is as follows:

What are the obstacles and drivers multinational LSPs face in their attempt to incorporate sustainability in their business operations?

1.3 Purpose & Contribution

The study intends to delve into the approaches taken by multinational Logistic Service Providers (LSPs) to tackle the issue of environmental sustainability by digging deeper into the industry's practical incorporation of the environmental aspect in connection to their economic goals. This question becomes all the more relevant in today's businesses, where policy

regulations are pressured to be incorporated in day-to-day practices and the overarching balance between economic and environmental targets is of stark importance. More specifically, our research focus is directed towards the identification of potential drivers and barriers to sustainability including their respective motivations. The purpose of this study is thus to increase understanding of the challenges LSPs face and to which degree internal and external forces are working together or against each other in this process. The results of this study are, therefore, on the one hand, a contribution to academic literature which is still lacking a deeper understanding of multinational LSPs and further requires updated insights from the industry. On the other hand, this paper also has practical implications for LSPs, as it can be used to understand motivations and guide towards solving the challenge between the two sustainability dimensions.

To gain a deeper understanding of the industry's sustainability approach and to answer this research question, qualitative research was deemed most appropriate. Through semi-structured interviews with employees from several multinational LSPs, we could get an insight into the practices and challenges these companies face. Furthermore, we supported these interviews with an analysis of public documents such as CSR-reports and information from the companies' websites to gain a 360° view on the companies' approaches to sustainability. Sustainability is a broad topic to cover and even with a narrowed focus on just the economic and environmental sustainability we still face an extensive field of research which is why we based our practices on previous research and acknowledged theory (Elkington, 1997; Creswell, 2014).

1.4 Outline of the Paper

This paper is structured as follows: After this introduction, the literature review sheds light onto previous research efforts and gives an overview of the topic from an academic point of view. Then the theoretical foundation of this paper is laid out accordingly with Elkington's Triple Bottom Line concept and the use it has for this research. Afterwards, the methods of this paper are introduced including the methodology and design of this study. The results of this study are presented in Chapter 4 and discussed in Chapter 5. The paper concludes with a summary of the findings and recommendations for further research.

2. Literature & Theory

2.1 Literature Review

2.1.1. Sustainability in the Logistics Sector

When it comes to sustainability and what it entails in practice, there seems to be a disparity between perception and reality resulting in a somewhat broken link between these two notions. In the logistics sector, environmental sustainability was introduced in the 1960s but only in the 1990s did academic researchers initiate intensifying research within the field (McKinnon, 2015). Even though academic articles have repeatedly demonstrated that logistics sector firms are, in theory, concerned about sustainability and its effects linked to their operation (Lieb & Lieb, 2010; Abbasi & Nilsson, 2016; Evangelista, 2014) the actual environmental measures convey a different picture. Transportation is the only sector that Eurostat (2020) has identified as showcasing an increase in both energy consumption and Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions between 1990 and 2017. The combination of globalisation together with unprecedented high consumption levels has contributed to a growing industry (European Commission, 2011) that only struggled briefly in the aftermath of the 2008 financial crisis. Since 2013 the emission levels of the logistics sector are noticeably increasing again (Eurostat, 2020) which stands in direct contrast to academic research results (Lieb & Lieb, 2010). In their 2010 survey, Lieb and Lieb interpreted the effects of the financial crisis on the LSPs' sustainability practices specifically. Most of the companies claimed that the crisis came to no obstacle to their sustainability goals and further insisted that sustainability will be one of the most important trends in the industry in the upcoming years (PwC & APICS, 2014). So, how can this disparity between idea and practice be explained?

Wu and Dunn (1995) identified early on an overall internal conflict within the logistics sector between economic and environmental performance as being one possible explanation. The long-term effects of environmentally friendly operations are not always foreseeable and are thus weighted against the short-term costs such investments needed (Wu & Pagell, 2011). In an industry, where time is an influential factor and price competition is fierce, every additional cost is evaluated thoroughly (Wolf & Seuring, 2010). Other possible explanations include market dynamics, culture, transparency and organisational processes and are explained in the following sections.

2.1.2 The Increasing Importance of LSPs in the Market

It seems that the majority of research conducted on sustainability in the supply chain has been focused on Logistic Service Providers (LSPs). As most manufacturers outsource their logistics operations, that task was given to LSPs thus making both their market share and their influence on the logistics market and business practices grow; including sustainability (Maas et al., 2014). Though, the fact that they operate outsourced contracts also results in tough price competition (Piecyk & Björklund, 2015). Consequently, LSPs are pressured to cut costs, placing sustainability lower in the industry's priorities, or even leaving it outside of the equation. These price pressures also result from competition within the industry, because the market is dominated by a few large, worldwide operating companies such as DHL, DB Schenker, C.H.Robinson and Kuehne+Nagel. The twenty largest 3PLs make about 24% of the global revenue, or 225bn USD respectively (Statista, 2020c; Statista, 2020d). These large players can form the market significantly in both economic and environmental terms. In fact, despite questionable cost-effectiveness, several researchers have shown that some LSPs have found environmental sustainability to be of economic interest, despite the aforementioned issues that may tag along with it (Ding, Liu & Zheng, 2016; Evangelista, 2014; Evangelista, Colicchia & Creazza, 2017; Lee & Wu, 2014). In those cases, sustainability is usually perceived as a feature that can act as a differentiation factor between otherwise all too similar LSPs (Evangelista et al., 2017; Maas et al., 2014). On that note, others found that the dilemma between cost efficiency and environmental sustainability can be solved by adding a premium on the price (Ding et al., 2016). Thereby, environmental sustainability becomes economically attainable for LSPs but also a potential luxury product for customers. In such cases, customers are thus considered more of a barrier rather than a driver towards sustainability because cost efficiency is valued more than environmental sustainability.

In other cases, customers were identified to be a driving force for LSPs to improve their own sustainability. Wolf and Seuring (2010) have shown that some companies are actively forcing LSPs to become green by incorporating it in the contracts or working exclusively with green LSPs. Since LSPs are dependent on the manufacturers for mandates, customers are effectively able to dictate environmental sustainability for the sector to a certain degree.

The third actor that should be considered in the game of sustainability in the logistics sector is the government. National governments all around the globe have set environmental goals and since 2015 international agreements have been established to be implemented by governmental and private sector decision-makers (UNFCCC, 2020). While some goals are merely

suggestions, making them more or less voluntary to be applied, national governments especially have the power to enact additional regulations that have to be followed (Elkington, 1997). These regulations, though fairly recent, seem to have effects on the logistics sector. More specifically, El Baz and Laguir (2017) identified that many LSPs follow a rather reactive approach to sustainability and with government regulations, this reactive approach can be supported. As Ding et al. (2016) have shown, tightening regulations step by step allows LSPs to adapt gradually and to spread out initial investment costs. However, these mandatory costs that come with regulations are still perceived as a barrier to sustainability by some companies (Oberhofer & Dieplinger, 2014). In these cases, the government may help overcome such costs with incentives or alike thereby promoting sustainability (Ding et al., 2016). The governmental effects on sustainability, however, might not be restricted by borders. As El-Baz and Laguir (2017) indicated in their research on Moroccan LSPs companies with close ties to or mother-companies in Europe are more likely to be affirmative towards environmental sustainability as well. The strict regulations in Europe influence the business operations to such a level that LSPs have to adapt their entire concepts to sustainability. Consequently, the companies with headquarters in Europe become trendsetters and shape the industry even outside the European borders. This is further supported by the fact that out of the 50 largest LSPs half are home in Europe. The government has, therefore, a similar role to customers in terms of influence: executed right, it may act as a driver and motivator for more green practices with the potential risk of being too demanding, therefore, becoming a barrier. However, claiming that only external factors are the deciding force for LSPs is misleading as well, which leads over to the next section that discusses internal conflicts of sustainability.

2.1.3 Sustainability in the Eyes of LSPs

Many scholars have shown that internal operations are not to be neglected when discussing environmental sustainability. Yang et al. (2013) studied the effects of internal and external practices on environmental performance. Their *results highlight the direct effect of external green collaboration on green performance and firm competitiveness, but [also] highlight the indirect effect of internal green practices on firm competitiveness* (p.69). These internal practices vary greatly from company to company (Greschner Farkavcova et al., 2018), but some processes are similar and will be discussed herein detail; namely strategy formulation, CSR reports, performance tracking and employee involvement.

Crafting a clear business strategy is a common management practice to formulate goals and motivate employees. Ultimately, it helps form an organizational structure and to achieve the set goals (Bolman & Deal, 2013). Therefore, some companies began to either include environmental sustainability in their overall strategy or to formulate a separate green strategy. Maas et al. (2014) noticed in their analysis of LSPs that a clear set of goals and strategies can make the subject more tangible to managers and employees. It has further been highlighted by PwC and APICS (2014) that there exists a certain degree of miscommunication between managers and employees regarding sustainability. The abstract goals of the higher levels might be difficult to execute for the lower levels in the organization which tends to result in inaction. Therefore, a straightforward goal might help motivate both the higher and lower levels at LSPs. Another point where internal conflict might arise due to lack of clarity is in cases where performance is not transparently measured. Environmental performance in contrast to economic success is not as quantifiable and is also highly debated among researchers. Some argue that the easiest way is to look at freights' CO₂ emissions. However, this measure leaves out other GHGs and only calculates CO₂ emissions of transportation, for instance, ignoring emissions made by other operations (El Baz & Laguir, 2017). Therefore, a more holistic approach towards the determination of environmental performance are measures such as the Life-Cycle Assessment (LCA) (Battini et al., 2014). The LCA calculates the environmental impact of the supply chain in total rather than individual parts giving a 360° view on the topic. For those evaluations to be accurate though, measures have to be made accessible internally again which is why Wu and Dunn (1995) have called on LSPs to improve their internal measurement practices: it would not just increase transparency within that particular company but estimates on the whole industry would improve. Additionally, these measures can be used to improve the company's image for example with CSR reports. These reports are mostly voluntary and Piecyk and Björklund (2015) found that only about 30% of large LSPs issue them. There is no clear correlation between reporting and improved performance but indirect effects on the image and internal accountability should not be dismissed (Wu & Pagell, 2011; Yang et al., 2013). It should further be noted that these reports are, like the strategies themselves, very diverse across the industry, no clear templates are used which leaves room for interpretation (Piecyk & Björklund, 2015). Internal green practices are thus more or less a direct result of other corporate processes which makes sustainability a matter of priority.

2.1.4 Conflict Potential: Environmental Sustainability & Economic Performance

Looking at the prioritisation within LSPs and most businesses, in general, economic profitability seems to dominate the top of the list. The reason for existence is usually to offer a service and make money in return – and environmental sustainability is not primarily part of this equation. Therefore, as soon as sustainability is incorporated in strategic planning it automatically collides with the overall goal of profitability. However, if the commitment to sustainability is strong enough, a certain balance between the two might be achieved (Wu & Pagell, 2011). Research has begun to explore this potentially conflicted relationship mostly by focusing on individual countries and comparing samples of LSPs against each other (Laari et al., 2016; Laari et al., 2018; Oberhofer & Dieplinger, 2014). The results were mixed as there was no clear indication with regards to whether green practices have a direct effect on operational or financial performance (Laari et al., 2016; Laari et al., 2018). As aforementioned, the heterogeneous evaluation practices might be one of the deciding factors for these mixed results which is why other researchers have focused their attention on the decision-making process within LSP firms (Shi et al., 2019; Lee & Wu, 2014). Shi et al. (2019) coined the Sustainable Transportation Model (STM) which displays the complex decision-making process and highlights the possibility to balance not just economic performance and environmental sustainability but also the social sustainability dimension². Lee and Wu (2014) took a similar approach using a different model with comparable results. According to the authors, the key to a more sustainable firm is a decision-making process that includes not just environmental information as such but information on the balance between environment and profit. Thereby, the process takes into consideration not just short-term benefits but also long-term interests. However, they also stress that logistics should not be overlooked in these processes. Even though internal managerial practices might, on paper, increase environmental performance more, neglecting the possibility in projects such as reducing fuel consumption of the truck fleet will ultimately also be needed.

2.1.5 Summary of the Literature Review

Academia has started to make a practical sense of the balance between economic performance and environmental sustainability, but the results are still limited. It seems that the approach

² More on the three sustainability dimensions (triple bottom line model) in Section 2.2

LSPs are taking is rather individual with few patterns to be identified. Both, the external demand for environmental sustainability – including customer relation and governmental influence – and internal operations seem to affect the industry, it is just unclear how these factors are all brought together to avoid conflict. One common idea taken up by researchers and companies alike is the idea of a sustainability approach based on three dimensions (Abbasi & Nilsson, 2016; Lee & Wu, 2014; Shi et al., 2019). Researchers have called for a deeper look into this model and its implications which is what this study will focus on. The next section breaks down this model before proceeding with the methodology.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

The term sustainability has been around for a long while, but to the business world, the concept seems to still be fairly new. Elkington (1997) in his much-cited book ‘Cannibals with Forks: The Triple Bottom Line of the 21st-century business’ defined sustainability for the business world as *the principle of ensuring that our actions today do not limit the range of economic, social, and environmental options open to future generations* (p.20). This definition highlights the three interconnected dimensions of sustainability that ultimately interact with each other: economic, social, and environmental. Elkington uses the term ‘Triple Bottom Line’ (TBL) to showcase that businesses should be concerned about more than just economic performance. The relationships between the bottom lines will be further explained but first, it is necessary to define the three dimensions individually.

2.2.1 The Economic Bottom Line

The economic bottom line is the most comprehensible for most businessmen since the purpose of any business is usually to ensure profitability and return on investment. Traditionally, this dimension included both financial and physical capital considering both liquidity and assets. For this dimension, performance tracking is facilitated using common measures such as Return on Investment (ROI), Return on Assets (ROA) or Earnings Before Interest and Taxes (EBIT) (Carey, Knowles & Towers-Clark, 2017). The time span such measures cover varies between a month and a year meaning there is constant tracking and also constant pressure (Elkington, 1997). It is accountability to shareholders that drives companies to disclose information on this bottom line and report figures on profitability. To ensure profits not just for the next reporting period but also beyond accountants have found measures to prolong costs such as depreciation

(Carey et al., 2017). Economic sustainability thus comes with the goal of ensuring profits for shareholders over time.

2.2.2 The Social Bottom Line

Social concerns in business operations started with slavery and child labour and developed to calls for education and equality as well as safety and partnership (Elkington, 1997). This bottom line concerns what became popular as human and intellectual capital. It stresses the importance of the human factor, namely all employees and intangible assets a company possesses. Factors such as employee satisfaction, labour safety, employee turnover, gender equality, diversity and training are measures that companies might use internally. Furthermore, this bottom line also covers external measures such as charitable donations and partnerships with customers and suppliers. All in all, social sustainability can be summed up in value terms including trust, loyalty, and dependability; terms that together form a healthy and sustainable foundation for businesses that are usually found under the well-known umbrella term of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). Companies are composed of employees and keeping certain working standards assessing their needs and rights is vital and falls under the management's responsibility and accountability to ensure that these standards are met on the highest of levels.

2.2.3 The Environmental Bottom Line

While climate change can be seen as a rather common-sense fact (UNFCCC, 2020) the responses to and handling of it have so far been comparatively diverse. Environmental sustainability concerns the idea that the current generation has a responsibility to preserve the natural resources in a way that does not restrict future generations (Elkington, 1997). This intergenerational responsibility includes not just the availability of 'natural capital' but also the quality of living, measured by performance indicators such as GHG emissions and noise. For businesses, this bottom line translates primarily to awareness of external side effects: their actions do not happen in a vacuum but have real-life environmental effects and these effects should be accounted for in internal measures and where possible also in the product prices (internalization of externalities). The driving force behind corporate efforts are in most cases governmental regulations or media campaigns but even customers can influence a company's environmental accountability.

2.2.4 The Triple Bottom Line Model

Elkington calls on businesses to include a holistic approach to sustainability in their operations and to rely on a TBL strategy to master the challenges of capitalism in the 21st century. By evaluating all stages of the supply chain, the problems that occur become more easily identifiable to solve, since sustainability issues may occur from the first to very last stage of the process painting a picture that is even closer to reality and thus urged by scholars to be prioritized (Battini et al., 2014). In an ideal world, the three sustainability criteria would be seen not as separate entities but as one concept of sustainability – similar to Figure 1. Elkington (1997) expresses this need for a unified concept as follows: *society depends on the economy - and the economy depends on the global ecosystem, whose health represents the ultimate bottom line* (p.73). It is therefore impossible to build sustainability on only one or two dimensions. In his analogy, the dimensions can be viewed as tectonic plates which are constantly fluctuating, moving independently from each other (Figure 2). However, Elkington (2018) also acknowledges that full integration of all three dimensions is challenging to businesses and that therefore *at minimum, progress on two dimensions [should be made] while the third remains unaffected* (p.4). Graphically speaking, integrating two of the three dimensions creates the possibility to move these towards the constant third.

Figure 1. The Triple Bottom Line (ideal version)

Figure 2. The Triple Bottom Line with shearzones

Figure 2 also shows another crucial part of Elkington's theory: the shearzones. They describe the potential conflict areas between sustainability dimensions. In the best case, the tectonic plates meet and unite – without clash – but in many cases friction between sustainabilities cannot be avoided which then results in tension – or translated, in company internal conflict. These shearzones are numbered and represented here according to the biggest challenge of their respective conflict area: the first one – 'Eco-efficiency' – describes the conflict between economic and environmental bottom line, the second – 'Environmental Justice' – between environmental and social, and the third one – 'Business Ethics' – between social and economic. Eco-efficiency refers to *the delivery of competitively-priced goods and services that satisfy human needs and bring quality of life, while progressively reducing ecological impacts and resource intensity throughout the life cycle, to a level at least in line with the Earth's estimated carrying capacity* (Elkington, 1997, p.78). Within this shearzone, the potential conflict between profit and planet is weighted and challenges such as GHG taxes, internalization and shadow pricing are to be faced. Environmental justice includes what has been pointed out above as the intergenerational responsibility to preserve natural resources. It further consists of intragenerational responsibility which means that equity should be divided equally among everyone alive highlighting conflicts for example between more and less economically powerful parts of the world. Lastly, Business Ethics concerns both a company's internal and external ethical behaviour. Typical challenges in this shearzone include fair trade and minority rights but may vary greatly from country to country and even between companies.

2.2.5 The 7 Revolutions & 39 Steps to Sustainability

All three shearzones describe areas of conflict that a company will need to face if it strives for sustainability. Elkington also lines out in his book which steps have to be taken by corporations to prepare for or even avoid these conflicts altogether. He describes seven revolutions that are needed to arrive at a sustainable capitalist society:

1. Markets
2. Values
3. Transparency
4. Life-Cycle Technology
5. Partnerships
6. Time
7. Corporate Governance

These seven revolutions can be seen as seven aspects of business that need to be transformed to achieve sustainability. Each of these aspects or revolutions comprises several concrete steps – totalling to 39 steps – that corporations have to take to incorporate the full TBL strategy (see Figure 3). These steps correspond to a general rethinking of old sustainability paradigms and practices (or lack thereof), which is also the explanation for why the term ‘revolution’ makes sense here: sustainability can only be achieved by radical new thinking. The enumeration of the revolutions, however, does not imply a timeline; the revolutions can and do happen simultaneously, with different speeds and yet also partly rely on each other in their implementation. Simply put, the 39 steps are a manual for businesses to move the tectonic plates closer together while avoiding a clash and with the ultimate goal of becoming sustainable. Within each aspect of business operations (revolution), rethinking is needed, and strategies need to be adapted to arrive at the full implementation of a TBL strategy which corresponds to sustainable business practices in Elkington’s view.

Figure 3. The 39 steps to sustainability within corporations

Old Paradigm		→	New Paradigm	
Markets				
1	externalization of costs	→	internalization of costs	
2	compliance	→	competitive advantage	
3	country-by-country standards	→	global consistency	
4	adding volume	→	adding value	
5	production growth	→	sustainable consumption	
6	disruptive NGO campaigns	→	disruption as commercial strategy	
Values				
7	careless, uncaring	→	careful, caring	
8	control	→	stewardship	
9	me	→	we	
10	monocultures	→	diversity	
11	growth	→	sustainability	
Transparency				
12	closed except financial reports	→	open, triple bottom line reports	
13	need to know	→	right to know	
14	facts and science	→	emotions and perception	
15	one-way communication	→	multi-way, active dialogue	
16	promises	→	targets	
Life Cycle Technology				
17	responsibility to factory gate	→	stewardship throughout life-cycle	
18	sales	→	lifetime customer value	
19	product waste	→	co-products	
20	environmental LCAs	→	triple bottom line LCAs	
21	product	→	function	
22	trial and error	→	biomimetics	
Partners				
23	deregulation	→	reregulation	
24	enemies	→	complementors	
25	subversion	→	symbiosis	
26	unconditional loyalty	→	conditional loyalty	
27	rights	→	responsibilities	
28	green business networks	→	sustainability keiretsu	
Time				
29	wider	→	longer	
30	extraction	→	restoration	
31	tactics	→	strategy	
32	plans	→	scenarios	
33	time bandits	→	time guardians	
Corporate Governance				
34	financial bottom line	→	triple bottom line	
35	physical and financial capital	→	economic, human, social, natural	
36	tangible, owned assets	→	intangible, borrowed assets	
37	downsizing	→	innovation	
38	exclusive governance	→	inclusive governance	
39	shareholders	→	stakeholders	

In the first revolution, companies will face the challenges of globalization and international competition. At the same time, the market will need to adapt to customer demand for sustainability, thereby changing not just internal pricing but also the products themselves.

The second revolution will require companies to overthink their code of conduct. During this revolution people come more into focus and values taken for granted should be reconsidered.

Transparency, as the third revolution, will not just uncover the progress from the previous revolutions but also allow for the next ones to be accountable. Through outside pressure not just from customers but also shareholders businesses will have to become transparent about their green and social practices not just their financial operations. Thereby the focus shifts from the ‘need to know’ to the ‘right to know’.

In the fourth revolution, the products themselves get more into focus. It will become increasingly popular to report all stages of a product’s life cycle, from the raw materials to disposal. Moreover, the improvement of products to reduce waste or to create side-products will be needed to keep up with sustainability.

With the fifth revolution, the attention will shift to outside actors. The importance of cooperation among businesses within the same field but also with political institutions and campaigning groups will grow. To achieve sustainability, partnerships will be required that are

based on the same ideals which makes loyalty conditional among businesses but also leaves possibilities for rivalling parties to come together under a common goal.

Time as the sixth revolution will play a crucial role in the progress as it pulls in two directions simultaneously. The globalized world is getting accustomed to fast delivery and instant communication while sustainability is a long-shot project. Hence, it will require businesses to rethink plans into scenarios while also monitoring time rather than only counting it down.

In the last revolution, Corporate Governance will be questioned. As Elkington (2014) expressed it: *the best way to ensure that a given corporation fully addresses the TBL agenda is to build the relevant requirements into its corporate DNA from the very outset* (p.6). It is here where the priority from the financial bottom line should be questioned in favour of a triple bottom line.

This is also where we come back to the incorporation of the three bottom lines. The call for a holistic approach within the logistics sector has been made by academia. And while the inclusion of social concerns is not necessarily extraordinary for this industry, the focus on environmental sustainability might be. As depicted earlier, the logistics sector has been struggling with this implementation even though the concept has been around for some time now. Elkington predicted in his book that *most medium-term progress, in fact, is likely to be made against the first and second bottom line (economic and environmental)* (Elkington, 1997, p.94). It is now 20 years later, making it an appropriate time to reevaluate this relationship and track progress on its implementation and effects. This paper will, therefore, use Elkington's TBL model and especially the idea of the 39 steps and seven revolutions to identify current behaviour, assess whether these steps indeed soften the tension within shearzones and, ultimately, which obstacles need to be overcome to achieve overall sustainability. Figure 4 shows the theoretical framework against which the chosen LSPs will be evaluated. For simplicity, the Figure shows the seven revolutions instead of the 39 steps. But in the process it will become clear that, for a narrow assessment, both will need to be taken into consideration. It should also be noted that this study – as explained in Chapter 1 – will focus on the relation between the environmental and economic bottom line. We thereby follow the idea that incorporation of these two offers the LSPs in our study the chance to keep the social bottom line constant and move the other two first.

Figure 4. Theoretical Framework

2.2.6 Limitations of the Theoretical Framework

Even though the theoretical framework given by Elkington (1997) is quite comprehensive, it also has some limitations that might interfere with parts of our analysis. First of all, the seven revolutions and the corresponding 39 steps are accustomed to a model which includes all three sustainability dimensions. In our adapted version of the model, there might thus be lacks or unclear answers to some steps. Practically speaking, Step 32 for instance – ‘diversity’ – might not be mentioned by interviewees because the focus of the interview questions is on environmental sustainability and not social aspects. Secondly, Elkington’s model is largely applicable to but not specifically designed for the logistics sector. So, it might happen that certain concepts are not well suited for this particular sector (e.g. LCAs). Such cases will be explained in the discussion section. Thirdly, Elkington’s approach is – despite its long-lasting popularity – over 20 years old. It does not include milestones of environmental measurement and goals such as the Kyoto Protocol (1997) and the Paris Agreement (2016). Since the publication of Elkington’s book, the world has changed which is why the analysis of previous literature provides a back-up frame for the analysis. Last but not least, the 39 steps are a directive tool and not a guarantee for sustainability. This is because the model suggests that all companies and all entities of a market would need to follow it to be on the right path. To sum up, our research findings might indicate already sustainable companies or industries without it being true. The margin of interpretation is probably the biggest limitation Elkington’s model has and because of that, the analysis of the companies will need to adapt accordingly. The possibility of misinterpretation is common in qualitative research and will also be discussed in

Chapters 5 and 6. However, previous research efforts are assisting here as well and offer an alternative framework where needed.

3. Method

3.1 Scientific Approach to the Study

The underlying philosophies of science for this paper have been mainly drawn by Bhaskar's (2008) critical realism principles. The central theme of these principles can be summed up in the fact that social phenomena may be approached in similar ways as physical phenomena; the primer difference being that instead of a traditional positivist nature will be observed and interpreted through the lenses of critical realism. The goal of this paper is thus to increase understanding of the relationship between environmental sustainability and traditional business strategies including future possibilities and challenges in their path of having achieved or intending to achieve whilst abiding by certain policies and regulations.

According to Lijphart, *the greatest advantage of the case study is that ... that case can be intensively examined even when the resources at the investigator's disposal are relatively limited* and this is what we hope to have achieved from the generated findings (in Moses & Knutsen, 2019, p. 139). That led us to choose to focus on LSPs in the logistics sector as our source of case data to fulfil its purpose. Furthermore, this research decided to make use of the multiple case study methodology since, as argued by Eisenhardt (1989) and Creswell (2014), this is deemed fitting when dealing with research within a territory that is not deeply explored as is the logistics sector in that regard due to LSPs still struggling to find solutions on how to best integrate sustainability into their operations as aforementioned (Colicchia et al., 2013). The next step was to assess the direction of the approach taking into account the purpose of our study as well as our resources in the given timeframe. Therefore, the chosen qualitative approach was translated into conducting in-depth semi-structured interviews with employees of the four LSPs we were able to interview. Interviews would tell us more than mere reports and numbers which would, in turn, help us understand the logistics sector in that regard internally whilst also acquiring a perspective of how the situation is being assessed by the respective companies and how they are planning to eventually become sustainable. This decision was further strengthened as it aligned with Oberhofer and Dieplinger's (2014) statement that *the fact that costs and economic consequences are sensitive topics for a company supports the choice of a qualitative approach* (p.239). Moreover, we aimed to uncover the variations in the theoretical framework generated from our analysis with Elkington's concepts (see Chapter 2.2) which we partially achieved making our findings applicable to similar settings. That being said, we restrain from generalising our findings in the industry for most

parts as we are aware of it being quite a diverse field resulting in business strategies in terms of sustainability to vary greatly from one LSP to another, even among the larger ones.

3.2 Research Design

3.2.1 Sampling

Our research focuses on multi-national LSPs because of their reach and influence in the market which is why we adopted a systematic sampling technique to identify the units of the study (Bryman & Bell, 2011). Our initial sampling frame was a list of the largest LSPs (measured by revenue) (Armstrong & Associates, 2019) and we ensured that each of them operates in more than one country. We then excluded the LSPs that are headquartered outside of Europe because we wanted to ensure a common cultural influence on the business operations. As El Baz and Laguir (2017) indicated in their research, there are hints on different approaches to sustainability relating to the headquarters of an LSP. Through this exclusion, the list of the 50 largest LSP providers worldwide narrowed down to 16. In the first row, we contacted nine of these companies via email. In almost all cases we were able to contact at least two different offices or contact persons, respectively. Unfortunately, the response rate was quite low which is why we decided to not just contact the remaining 5 but to expand our sample and include medium-sized multinational LSPs. That gave us the possibility to look at the dynamics between LSPs again and see whether the large ones influence the others when it comes to day-to-day business and sustainability. We found another 16 companies through an extensive Google search, most of which we were only able to contact one office. Eventually, the total number of contacted offices was 61 of which we were able to interview five employees from four different companies. Many of the companies, even some of which we ended up interviewing, were hesitant to participate because of increased stress levels due to the on-going SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. Almost all contacted companies had disclaimers on their website advising customers, partners, and journalists about changed office hours and/or change in business operations. The low response rate is, therefore, to be judged against the circumstances and we concluded that a sample of 4 companies and 5 interview partners would suffice for our study given that falls under the number required for qualitative research (Creswell, 2014).

3.2.2 Data Collection Technique

We gathered two sets of data in an attempt to have a holistic approach when answering our research question. The first set of data was gathered first hand and embraces a constructivist

methodology making use of semi-structured interviews to gain insight into the employee's experience in the respective company that is tackling the issue of environmental sustainability (Bryman & Bell, 2011). The second set of data includes the four LSPs' financial and sustainability reports. This approach was intended to reflect the company's operations fulfilling together with both sets of data the purpose of us gathering material to analytically answer our research question on their sustainability practices hermeneutically interpreting the transcribed interviews in combination with their publicly available reports on the matter. More importantly, it increased the validity of our research as we could compare the two data sets and conduct follow up and open-ended questions to keep both a professional and honest interview with the participants who offered their time for our research.

3.2.3 Operationalisation

In the process of operationalisation, we set up an interview guide that corresponded to the themes that we wanted to discuss with the four multinational LSPs which we will from now on referring to as Company A, B, C and D respectively. More specifically, the themes covered topics and concepts such as sustainability in the logistics sector, the increasing importance of LSPs in the market, sustainability in the eyes of LSPs and potential conflicts between environmental sustainability and economic performance (see Chapter 2). The main interest of avoiding conflict between bottom lines was thus translated into questions addressing the ways their company handles these issues in their operations. As our theory suggests a process with seven revolutions (Elkington, 1997), we based our interview guide on these aspects of business and the corresponding 39 steps. However, to give the interviewees the freedom to express their personal experience with the topic we decided to reformulate some of Elkington's ideas and to make the questions more open for interpretation, thereby also adapting to previous research findings. The interview guide, therefore, represents a loose adaptation of Elkington's seven revolutions and previous research while the coding scheme takes the 39 steps as an initial tool of analysis with the possibility to adapt, if necessary.

3.2.4 Procedure

The first step for us was to contact the companies that we previously decided to include in our sample (see 3.2.1). These companies were either contacted via email or using a contact form on the website. We then scheduled interviews conducted on Skype, Zoom and Microsoft Teams, respectively. Since all contacted companies had their headquarters outside of Stockholm and

also due to the on-going pandemic, remote interviews were the only option for us. Before the interview, all participants received the interview guide for preparation (Burnard, 1991; Oberhofer & Dieplinger, 2014). Whilst interviewing we made notes in addition to recording to collect details about the tone and certain aspects that stood out for extra useful material. The interviews took between 25 and 55 minutes, depending on the interviewees' availability. Shortly after the interview, both of us proceeded with transcribing the entirety of the interview and shared notes whilst reflecting upon the fresh material which resulted in quite an amount of supplemental data to analyse later on. After our first round of analysis, we decided to send back to the interviewees the quotes and main points we were planning to use for our thesis to ensure that we had correctly interpreted the participants' views. This last part, though not necessary, is highly recommended and not just increased the study's validity (Burnard, 1991) but also offered the chance to get some feedback for enriching our analysis.

3.3 Data Analysis

First and foremost, it must be underlined that the overarching focus of this study is the growing tension of the sustainability dimensions. In other words, the multifaceted nature of sustainability acted as a compass in our analysis of both the conducted interviews and the secondary data. To analyse our raw data, we used a coding scheme fitting the theoretical framework we used as lenses in this study. To be more specific, we used Elkington's 39 steps according to which we highlighted the transcribed interviews as well as their respective public material. We had read through the transcript taking notes and sorting themes before sending out the ideas to our interviewees again. Some themes were eventually tailored accordingly whilst finalising the coding scheme placing the participants' quotes under the identified themes. We applied the same strategy when going through the secondary data. That way we managed to process two different sets of data in similar ways which were of big aid when looking for facts, words, or quotes and sayings that could either confirm, falsify or add more information than we would have gotten by analysing only one of the two data sets. It was deemed unnecessary to plan a new framework for the separate data sets as they derived from the same companies.

3.4 Ethical Reflection

Considering this is a qualitative study ethical matters should be discussed here. We conducted this research following recognized ethical standards outlined by Bryman and Bell (2011). To the best of our knowledge, no one was harmed by this research and due to anonymisation of the

participants, we hope to protect the interviewees as well as the companies they work for from potential impairment. The interviewees in this study all participated voluntarily and gave their consent to be recorded and cited for this paper. As secondary data, only such public material was considered that could be found on the companies' official channels and anonymised in the same way as the first data set. All personal data as well as data that identifies the companies or participants, including their position within the company, is stored under current law, and made available only with consent of the participants.

3.5 Assessment Quality

Since we are two students working on this project it is important to check with each other and individually that our research is credible and dependable throughout the process. We tried to achieve that by making use of Bryman and Bell's (2011) criteria as well as constantly reflecting that we are on the right track regarding this research and make careful use of both language and argumentation. We relied our study on an existing model and well-known techniques to be able to increase measurement and internal validity. What was limited in our study is the generalisability – in other words, external validity – within the context of large LSPs. That being said, the external validity is highly aimed to begin with considering the nature of this study which is a qualitative case one (Welch, Piekkari, Plakoyiannaki & Paavilainen-Mäntymäki, 2011). Last but not least, reliability is indeed conveyed through thorough explanation of the research process as well as the interview guide. Though that does not offer maximum reliability, the limitations of our study were taken into consideration and were dealt with caution.

3.6 Weaknesses & Limitations

First and foremost, although the method and methodology described above has many advantages and fits our research purpose, inevitably there are some weaknesses and limitations that we came across along the conduction of this study. The most important one is that even though we managed to talk to the interviewees with the guiding compass of Elkington's 39 steps, we are aware that more information could have been gathered if the sample were bigger or more interviews had been conducted. We came to this realisation as with every new interview, we were gaining new information depending on the direction of the semi-structured interview and the topics that the interviewee was more focused on and more knowledgeable about throughout our talks with them. The same applies to the different perspectives they

offered to share with us in the sense that we would probably acquire even more diversity with a larger sample. Moreover, although we did cover the raw data as well as the reports by coding them according to the 39 steps, we are reserved for some amount of bias since we were pursuing to detect certain patterns according to these steps which may have led us to possibly miss other information despite our efforts of actively avoiding to fall into that loop.

4. Empirical Presentation & Analysis

4.1 Empirical Presentation

In this section, the results of our interviews – based on our coding scheme – are presented. Table 1 shows the participants of the study and their respective companies with a few key characteristics that are of interest to this study. Table 2 gives a first overview of these results which are then analysed later in this chapter. The table below shows which steps of Elkington’s seven revolutions are fulfilled by the individual companies. For each step, both interview and secondary sources are considered to gain a full picture. The answers are then categorized into ‘yes’, ‘no’ and ‘maybe’. ‘Yes’ refers to cases where the company has adapted its operations to a more sustainable, TBL thinking and acting. ‘No’ is stated if a company makes clear that it has not introduced this step yet. ‘Maybe’ stands for the cases in which the information given by the interview or the secondary sources is ambiguous. In some cases, ‘yes’ and ‘no’ are both applicable and in other cases, there is no information available indicated here with ‘-’. Simply put, if a company stated during the interview that they compensate for GHG emissions or include them in the price calculations and the CSR reports supported this claim then Step 1, ‘internalisation of costs’ could be categorised as ‘yes’. However, if the same company had contradicting statements in their CSR reports or it was only a goal that has not yet been realised, ‘yes & no’ would be applied. In cases where the statements from either interview or secondary material were vague and not supported by the other, ‘maybe’ was chosen.

Table 1. Sample overview

	Company A	Company B	Company C	Company D
Interviewees	Interviewee #1 Interviewee #2	Interviewee #3	Interviewee #4	Interviewee #5
Headquarter	France	Switzerland	Germany	Denmark
Size of Company	large	large	large	medium
Market focus	worldwide	worldwide	worldwide	Nordics/Baltics
Industry focus	none	none	none	none
Transportation modes	air, sea, road, rail	air, sea, road, rail	air, sea, road, rail	air, sea, road, rail
Categorisation	3PL; 4PL	3PL; 4PL	3PL; 4PL	4PL

Table 2. Empirical Presentation

Step Nr	Step	Company A	Company B	Company C	Company D
Markets					
1	internalization of costs	yes	yes	yes	no
2	competitive advantage	yes	yes	yes	yes & no
3	global consistency	yes	yes & no	yes & no	-
4	adding value	yes & no	yes	yes	yes & no
5	sustainable consumption	yes	yes	yes	yes
6	disruption as commercial strategy	yes	yes	yes	maybe
Values					
7	careful, caring	yes	yes	yes	yes
8	stewardship	yes	yes	yes	-
9	we	yes	yes	yes	yes
10	diversity	yes	yes	maybe	-
11	sustainability	yes & no	yes	yes	yes & no
Transparency					
12	open, triple bottom line reports	yes	yes	yes	yes & no
13	right to know	yes	yes	yes	maybe
14	emotions and perception	yes	yes	maybe	-
15	multi-way, active dialogue	yes	yes	yes	yes
16	targets	yes	yes & no	yes	maybe
Life Cycle Technology					
17	stewardship throughout life-cycle	yes (intentions) no (in practice)	yes	yes	no
18	lifetime customer value	yes	yes	yes	yes
19	co-products	-	-	-	-
20	triple bottom line LCAs	yes	no	maybe	no
21	function	-	-	yes	-
22	biomimetics	-	-	-	-
Partners					
23	reregulation	yes	yes	yes	-
24	complementors	yes	yes	yes	maybe
25	symbiosis	yes	yes	yes	-
26	conditional loyalty	yes & no	no (in terms of env. sustainability)	yes	yes & no
27	responsibilities	-	maybe	yes	-
28	sustainability keiretsu	yes	yes	yes	no
Time					
29	longer	yes	yes	yes	yes
30	restoration	-	yes	yes	no
31	strategy	yes	yes	yes	no
32	scenarios	no	no	no	no
33	time guardians	yes	yes	yes	maybe
Corporate Governance					
34	triple bottom line	yes	yes	yes	maybe
35	economic, human, social, natural	yes	maybe	yes	no (in terms of natural)
36	intangible, borrowed assets	maybe	maybe	maybe	yes
37	innovation	yes	yes	yes	yes
38	inclusive governance	yes	yes	yes	yes
39	stakeholders	yes	yes	yes	yes

The following sections describe the detailed findings of this study. As explained above the analysis follows the coding scheme of Elkington's (1997) 39 steps separated here according to the seven revolutions. In this analysis, however, we delve deeper into how the implementation of those steps looks like in the logistics sector.

4.2 Analysis

4.2.1 Markets

When it comes to the implementation of market-related sustainability measures, the LSPs seem to be on the right track as all four companies at least partially fulfil the corresponding steps. The ‘internalization of costs’ through emission compensation programmes or premium prices for conscious customers was mentioned by everyone, with a slight reluctance from Company D as they considered themselves to still be in the early stages of changes. However, not all emission costs are compensated for so far, and only Company B stated a clear carbon-neutral target while the other companies are striving for a mere reduction of the current total.

Sustainability, and especially environmental sustainability, was indicated by all companies to act as a differentiation factor among LSPs. All companies mentioned the importance of sustainability to customers and described it as a necessary one even referring to it as a *key selling potential* (Interviewee #3) and a *competitive advantage* (Interviewee #5). The three large companies have global goals (Step 3) for their economic and environmental performance measures while the medium company has no clear environmental targets yet. However, Company B implied differences in environmental importance in negotiations while Company C has additional national targets that are in some aspects even more ambitious than their global strategy. It was further implied that the strong environmental focus of these companies was influenced by the culture of the countries. One interviewee mentioned previous work experience with Asian LSPs and said that the European counterparts pay more attention towards sustainability as they not just add it as a feature but integrate it into their operations.

The demand for sustainable logistics is reflected in the services LSPs provide. Apart from greener logistics services some also started to offer environmentally-focused consulting and evaluation tools. It is also becoming more prominent for the LSPs to offer not just one type of transportation but a wide range, thereby contributing to the value of the service (Step 4) if availability plays along.

‘Sustainable consumption’ (Step 5) for LSPs reaches from using fewer fossil fuels to internal energy consumption. All companies indicated a commitment (depending on when they began incorporating sustainability in their business strategy) to both, and Company D mentioned that:

*In terms of sustainability, it is about complying with the general laws and regulations....
The higher the Euro Norms³, the more efficient and the more likely that customers will
choose that truck.*

All four LSPs were aware of the publicity that goes along with sustainable business practices. Ambitious targets and cooperation with NGOs were highlighted during some of the interviews to emphasise this form of ‘disruptive’ commercialization (Step 6).

4.2.2 Values

The business field has used value terms (e.g. quality, diversity, responsibility) for a long time, for ad campaigns, attracting buyers, shareholders, and investors. Sustainability is approached similarly: Companies seem to have unlocked keywords to use in both marketing companies and overall communication, selling points for the customers and business partners alike, trying to make themselves stand out. Although there is diversity in the way that is being portrayed externally, the large companies we targeted seem to have pinned down what they want to be distinguished for concerning sustainability. The medium one, on the other hand, acknowledged that they are not yet able to inflict such influence but did consider it as an abstract goal for the near future.

First of all, Company A wants to put forward the fact that its sustainability agenda is all about people. The company identifies sustainability as a holistic approach mentioning the importance of including the individuals involved in the process, repeating the ‘people’ aspect throughout the interview and how much significance they have begun to add to it.

... people [are] the biggest asset of the company. (Interviewee #1)

They underlined the importance of going back to basics by thinking about the people’s needs and wellbeing going as far as to state that *helping our environment* should be in the same wavelength of a mindset as to *maintain people’s health and welfare* all of which are included in Step 7.

On the same note, communication with clients and customers that value sustainability was detected as both a driver for the LSPs not only to elevate their standards and offer more sustainable solutions but also to incorporate the mindset of the limited natural resources that

³ Referring to the European emission standards for new vehicles

are shared by all. Company A described the above as a chain of reactions to a common issue that society faces today. One comment that stood out was that

It [sustainability] is really integrated more into our DNA. (Interviewee #2)

Overall, Company A shows an intergenerational responsibility where they acknowledge the expectation and pressure to step back from the *dirty business* (Interviewee #3), divest from fossil fuels and consider society's needs as well as the reality of limited natural resources for future generations.

Companies C and D seem to present a more constrained approach. Interviewees #4 and #5 underlined that their companies are undeniably operating under the reality of climate change in a feasible way. Interviewee #4 also mentioned the pragmatic restrictions of the change to greener solutions taking time and being not as profitable despite their intentions of divesting from fossil fuels for the society's well-being. Consequently, the change was slow and somewhat steady but the drive for more solutions to be implemented and more money to be invested in innovation was more a question of customer preference on price rather than the company's target and values. When asked about how their sustainability aligns with their profit margins, the answer was

It is not so much of a question about increasing profit but rather surviving.

And:

In the short run, maybe it has a negative effect on economic performance but in the longer run maybe it can generate better economic performance. (Interviewee #3)

What they hope to see in the future for sustainability to be more established than it is now is for the market to be favourable towards that change to aid the companies to see it as profitable gains before the problem escalates further. Additionally, Company C mentions the need for a collective effort from actors of decision-making power such as the market and the government as

... doing this change is not a one man's job. (Interviewee #3)

On the other hand, Company B and (to some extent) D, interestingly enough, made no mention of other value concepts. That being said, the approach Company B is taking in their sustainability efforts is still reflective of the three sustainability dimensions. Their CSR method is clearly based on several pillars including the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), however, their measurement is separated, meaning sustainability is not handled as an integrated, valued concept but they rather

... see many opportunities for sustainable development to grow profitability and to provide our customers with added value. (Company B, 2018)

4.2.3 Transparency

Transparency over sustainable practices has evolved greatly over time and all interviewees acknowledged that awareness more or less forced LSPs to open their books on these issues. The resulting reports on sustainability are still diverse and the processes to uncover internal sustainability practices are not necessarily standardized as indicated by the fact that

There is currently no international standard for emissions calculation. (Company C, 2017).

But first things first: being transparent about sustainability includes open, TBL focused reports (Step 12). All four companies that were interviewed publish CSR reports on their websites and provide additional information about their sustainability efforts. However, these CSR reports do not necessarily follow a coherent structure. Company A emphasises on the challenges and supply chain optimisation, leaving a separate chapter for sustainability, but without any figures apart from the number of sustainable awards and the targets they have set for the future, Company B includes a sustainability definition similar to the TBL but does not include any economic figures. Company C has CSR reports solely on a national level and globally only on the level of their mother company. Company C's Swedish CSR report, for instance, includes environmental and social measures along with a few key economic figures. It is noteworthy that the dimensions are discussed separately in all reports. The reports are thus open but not in TBL fashion. Only Company D included all three dimensions into one report, however, their CSR section of the annual report is only three pages long and the claims are not statistically

supported. It is only mentioned that in future reports measures for environmental sustainability might be included (Company D, 2019).

On the second part of transparency – ‘the right to know’ – all four companies score. All have shared information on sustainability in the past not just on their website but also on their social media handles (including LinkedIn, Twitter, and Facebook).

Step 14 of the coding scheme includes the importance of emotions over facts. While all companies acknowledge climate change and its implications, their individual perceptions are what seems to drive their efforts. One interviewee admitted it took some time to realize the gravity of climate change but now with higher awareness and urgency the importance to act on it is prominent (Interviewee #3). Interviewee #4 also named sustainability awareness as a driver for LSPs and compared it to the ongoing pandemic referring to urgency as the key motivator for action.

To achieve a ‘multi-way and active dialogue’ with stakeholders, Company B pioneers by sending out evaluations to suppliers, customers, and investors to obtain feedback concerning sustainability performance. Additionally, all interviewees highlighted the internal importance sustainability has on all management levels. It was commented that the interview conducted would have probably had the same outcome if the company’s CEO was interviewed instead (Interviewee #4) and another participant said that their CEO was an important figure for internal and external sustainability (Interviewee #1&2). Company D (2019), on the other hand, only mentions the importance of collaboration with stakeholders but does not define it in detail.

Lastly, for transparency, the importance of ‘targets’ (Step 16) should be highlighted. The three large LSPs’ targets for sustainability vary in degree and measurement but all in all, they are formulated as targets, not promises. Company B aims to have a complete carbon-neutral supply chain by 2030, Company C wants to reduce its CO₂ emissions by 50% by then. Only Company D has no targets nor promises justifying it with their young age. In distinct contrast, Company A has set up a whole framework that includes not just targets but baselines and process analysis to react to changes by setting up a dedicated team for sustainability goals that are aligned with several official policies that work on business excellence within the field. This company thus comes closest to evaluating sustainability not as a plan but as a ‘scenario’ (Step 32). Another feature of these targets is process evaluation. Company B keeps track of its performance with yearly targets. Interestingly, as one of their targets – offering only carbon-neutral LCL by 2020 – is already in effect today it reverted into a promise:

We promise to provide our customers with environmental friendly, sustainable and innovative supply chain solutions that will reduce our collective CO2 footprint and help stakeholders achieve their bold environmental targets (Company B's Website, 2020)

Here the fine details of the process towards sustainability become apparent. While targets for the future are seemingly better for sustainability than promises, promises about already existing processes might go in the same direction, nonetheless.

4.2.4 Life Cycle Technology

Revolution four looks at life cycle technology, which refers to sustainability along the supply chain. Companies should start taking responsibility for their products' and services' whole supply chain and over the whole lifetime of these as well. For LSPs, this life cycle is primarily related to supply chain analysis and support for customers. Company C specifically has a system in place

... to avoid, reduce and compensate CO2 emissions along the whole supply chain (Company C's Website, 2020)

and as indicated above Company B strives for a carbon-neutral supply chain by 2030. Since LSPs are offering the logistics services that manufacturers and customers should take into consideration for a life cycle analysis, these efforts might already fulfil Elkington's premises. This includes the idea of 'co-products' (Step 19). Many LSPs are working with LCLs (Less than Container Loads). LCLs are shipments that are less than standard cargo containers and LSPs are usually the ones pairing different LCLs to minimize shipping costs. This method and the optimization of freight routes that all four companies are aiming for are probably the closest ones can get to 'co-products' in the logistics sector. The same goes for 'function' (Step 21): the product of LSPs are services which are difficult to transform into functions. It is also more difficult for a service provider to mimic nature in its application leaving 'biomimetics' (Step 22) for very ambitious and innovative LSPs.

In the hope for 'lifetime customer value' (Step 18), the studied LSPs started offering additional services such as carbon emission evaluation tools and consulting services. However, the fierce price competition between LSPs (Interviewee #5) also means that customers do not necessarily commit to one LSPs for a lifetime, which explains Company D's realistic statement:

... we aim for long customer relationships. (Company D's Website, 2020)

Company B, as the only one committed to a full environmental supply chain analysis also requires all partners to have a code of conduct regulating social aspects, which makes them closest to achieving a TBL LCA (Step 20).

Creating a sustainable supply chain as a provider of supply chain solutions is thus more complicated than anticipated. LSPs play a crucial role in the supply chain of many other companies and can provide them with the necessary tools for increasing sustainability, but the challenge of profitability aggravates this process as well.

4.2.5 Partners

The logistics sector is a business highly driven by partners and business collaborations either they are contractors, suppliers, carriers, investors, or shareholders. Therefore, the interviews invested some time in finding out how those partnerships affect the overall sustainability levels of the company of question.

To be more specific, Company A informed us that 'reregulation' (Step 23) has become an additional driver and challenge at the same time for the company to go forward with the finalisation of new deals in that regard. Discussions are made on both (or more) ends of the deal and sometimes the constant exchange with suppliers and customers on regulations can be quite extensive and time-consuming. Company A noted that they observe a trend rising of what appears to be *good for our image*, however, challenges in specific countries with looser regulations around sustainability have occurred which is a *constant battle*. Similarly, Interviewee #5 mentions the importance of their ESG (Environmental, Social and Governance) image being a driving factor in that regard. Additionally, Company B's CSR report mentions that:

The better we succeed in supporting our customers with corresponding logistics solutions, the more sustainable our development will be (Company B, 2018).

During the interview, the employee further explained the extended role of such partnerships that act as 'complementors' (Step 24) as:

The other companies are needed for their evaluation tools to work, they take information from port, carriers etc for the tools and thereby add value for the customer
(Interviewee #3)

Similarly, Company C seems to operate on complementors under ‘symbiosis’ (Step 25). They admitted that there is no other way but to collaborate with governmental policies, the customers as well as the market for such drastic changes to be created with the appropriate measures for a successfully operating business field that prides on being sustainable. Finally, Company D revealed that they are still much reliant on their sub-suppliers and as a medium-sized company do not yet have the power of influence regarding their collaborations, yet they do plan to alter that in the future if possible.

Thus, the statement confirms the need for collaborative LSPs to obtain effective and sustainable LCAs. Moreover, Company B implemented ‘conditional loyalty’ (Step 26) to customers and suppliers only concerning their code of conduct which regulates social measures but not yet for environmental standards. That comes in contrast to Company C’s approach on the matter as they underline that:

Who we choose to work with and our ability to influence them are of direct importance if we want to achieve the goals we have set in terms of reduced environmental impact.
(Company C, 2017)

Company C also delves deeper into the practicalities on how this can be achieved on a more pragmatic level mentioning the intricate yet collaborative web of actors, otherwise known as ‘keiretsu’ (Step 28), who are dependent on each other to achieve their sustainability targets all giving high priority and focus to get rid of fossil fuel soon. More specifically:

It involves technique, the shift to new technology, liquid biogas, biodiesel, electricity hydrogen. And that is the main driver I would say. But ... to do that you need the OEMs [Original Equipment Manufacturers], you need the fuel producers, you need the government representatives (Interviewee #4)

4.2.6 Time

In this section, we asked the participants about their perception of time both in the sense of what pace does their delivery time to their customers seem to affect their green choices today and how they plan to achieve their sustainability goals in the near and far future.

To be more specific, Company A mentioned that the on-going pandemic makes it a *forced necessity* to use air freight instead of sea freight *sacrificing* their sustainability levels (Interviewee #2). They further stated that they were not willing to lose money nor customers at this point and that

To be honest, we are in the business to make money after all. (Interviewee #2)

That indicates, as all four companies have pointed out, that the rule of thumb is to operate cost-effectively rather than with a green mindset, even though short- and long-term interest must be aligned somehow. The approach to the matter seems to be weighed differently among the companies we interviewed.

More specifically, Company A constantly highlights the need for investment in innovation for sustainable solutions to be made more accessible, more normalised, and ultimately less costly compared to today. In their 2018 CSR report innovation takes up nearly half the space of the document emphasising their views on the matter and the direction they suggest they, and other companies, must take for a sustainably beneficially but also profitable business. Company B, on the other hand, seems not to be cost-driven per se when sustainability is included in the decision-making scale. In other words, the company appears to prioritise intergenerational responsibility (Step 33) instead, since:

... the way we do business today affects generations in 100 to 150 years. (Interviewee #3)

Company C is also putting forward that sentiment referring to the IPCC (International Panel on Climate Change) report that gives a solid timeline for businesses to be pressured from and elevates the acuteness of the issue of climate change. Moreover, Company C and D, while not mentioning the cost, do mention the restrictions of low to no alternatives they have despite the efforts and changes they have made thus far. ‘Strategy’ (Step 31) seems to be an established

drive for this company to become all the more sustainable as it not only offers a framework on how to operate, but also keeps their business relevant.

4.2.7 Corporate Governance

In the seventh revolution, the focus shifts back to internal operations. First up is the incorporation of all three, instead of just one bottom line in the decision-making process. Company B expresses this as follows:

We strive towards economic, social and environmental harmony (Company B's Website, 2020).

And as seen earlier, Interviewee #4 even said profit must be evaluated against the survival of the company. However, throughout this analysis, it also became clear that the conflict with economic sustainability is still pressuring LSPs. Even though the conflict is mentioned by all interviewees the consequences are not necessarily explained, and the secondary sources are even more reluctant to address conflict. This becomes more evident through Step 35: economic, human, social, and natural capital. While all companies acknowledge the importance of their employees and the need to protect the environment, none of the companies describes their capital in these distinct versions which, in turn, hints upon the financial capital remaining the decision-maker. While Company D does not project a clear environmental focus, their awareness of social capital is still to be distinguished. Firstly, as Interviewee #5 stated it is

... an increasing matter of employees whether their employer has an ambition towards achieving sustainability.

This implies that employees can very well act as a driver to sustainability too. Furthermore, Company D differentiates themselves from others – especially large LSPs – by working through subsidiary companies that have their own management and employees and even part ownership. Through this structure, employees are offered responsibility and empowerment that leads to motivation and success, according to Interviewee #5. It does not entail that Company D defines human – or natural – capital as being equally important to financial capital but their absence of physical capital and the awareness of their importance is striking.

Generally speaking, physical capital (e.g. trucks), seems to decrease in importance to all four LSPs (Step 36). All are working with carriers and Company C even has a special arrangement with their carriers where

It says [Company C] on their clothes, trucks and they are [Company C], but not employed by [Company C]. (Interviewee #4)

The LSPs thereby not just freed themselves from assets but also human capital. These practices are commonplace in the logistics sector and they also show again the importance of close cooperation between LSPs and carriers to achieve sustainability.

This brings us to the next step which focuses on ‘innovation’. As Company B describes it:

sustainability is highly related to our spirit of innovation. (Company B, 2018)

New technologies including all kinds of fuels and measurement techniques are in high demand. With pilot projects such as fully electric trucks (Company C), these new technologies are now being tested. And even though the results seem promising, the issue of profitability also puts a spoke in the LSPs’ wheel – quite literally. The electric truck, for instance, is considerably more expensive to run than diesel-fuelled trucks which means customers are more hesitant to make use of such technologies. In other cases, LSPs take sustainability in their own hands for example when it comes to

HVO which is a biodiesel ... that we can use today, and we use it as much as possible. So that is not dependent on the customers’ willingness to pay. We just do that. (Interviewee #4)

However, alternative fuels will not necessarily be enough to combat climate change and the availability of other technologies is still limited which is why LSPs also rely on OEMs to produce and innovate for them. Company A (2018), therefore, urges for more research and development so that the conversion from the *dirty business* is easier but also more profitable. As the last aspects of Corporate Governance, ‘inclusive governance’ (Step 38) and ‘stakeholders’ (Step 39) are to be discussed here. It was already indicated above that all four LSPs maintain a close relationship to their stakeholders, and while no company defines stakeholders specifically, they all make clear that not just investors are included here – or

shareholders – but also customers, employees, and cooperative networks. In the interviews, these aspects have not been discussed in detail but the mere mentioning of close cooperation between departments and management and employees (Company A) speaks for a trend.

5. Discussion

The previous section analysed the individual steps the four studied LSPs have taken towards sustainability. In the following section, these steps and strategies will be framed into the bigger context of the logistics sector and compared to previous research.

First and foremost, the results of our study have shown that there is a general awareness of the problem and even a consensus of urgency in the logistics sector. The interviewees were all conscious about the severity of the issue and concerned about sustainability in the future which proves previous research efforts. As Battini et al. (2014) have indicated in their research, environmental measures might just need time to be adapted. Two of the companies only initiated in the past five years an adaptation to clear sustainability strategies whilst one still has it on its to-do list. The phase of adaption and trial and error seems, however, to be longer than expected. Academics have been calling on the industry for over 20 years to act on the matter while practitioners within the business field claim that back then no one talked about it. This miscommunication is not unprecedented in the academic field which is why it is assumed that other factors may have given the logistics sector the kick it needed to pursue sustainability goals as of late. We will further elaborate on the study's generated findings through the various drivers and barriers the LSPs deal with on their path to sustainability.

One identified driver are governmental regulations. Although regulations have been claimed to act as drivers or barriers by Colicchia et al. (2013), our study is pointing towards slightly different results. Company C, for instance, has oriented themselves according to international policies including the Paris Agreement and UN development goals and the other LSPs also mentioned following similar regulations. At the same time, all companies acknowledged the forced limitations that tag along with such regulations. Nonetheless, none of the companies seems to perceive regulations as a negative aspect to adhere to but that they have rather accepted them as a necessary evil, or even a driver, proceeding the companies' realisation that change needs to start from somewhere.

A second influential actor that was highlighted by all five interviewees is the customer. The significance of customer-LSPs relation has been addressed repeatedly by previous research (e.g. Ding et al., 2016; Evangelista et al., 2017; Wolf & Seuring, 2010) and our results not only support but also reinforce that statement further. Especially for smaller LSPs, the customers appear to be the only driving force for all decisions. Even one of the large LSPs admitted that they need to offer what the customer demands which clearly confirms the level of customers' influence on the LSPs' operations. Cost-effectiveness seemed to have been in the highest

priority of customers which would consequently affect their choices, however, LSPs have noticed a shift lately where sustainability is gaining substantial interest from the customers' side disrupting the known buying pattern. Given that only some LSPs offer greener alternatives it thus illustrates a battle within the industry and between LSPs. As Centobelli et al. (2017) and Maas et al. (2014) have shown, sustainability might be a differentiation factor between LSPs that helps conscious customers make their decision. Our findings partly support this claim. While none of the interviewees clearly stated that customers choose their company solely due to their environmental profile, the three large LSPs acknowledged that their sustainability profile may have given them a competitive advantage overall. The medium-sized LSP also highlighted the bonus sustainability offers to the employees' view on the company underlining the indirect effects of sustainable operations (Yang et al., 2013).

However, coming back to the customers' influence on the LSPs, it is notable that Smokers et al. (2014) parallelise cost versus customer as a prisoner dilemma and thus should be discussed here. The notion that LSPs are in a constant battle for cost-effectiveness, and ultimately customers, is supported by our findings. The interviews underline that all four LSPs face the problem of competition between LSPs and the resulting price pressure that refrains them from pursuing more sustainable business operations. Customers demand low prices and quick delivery which so far can only be achieved through unsustainable (or not as sustainable) means, and as long as the customers do not alter their perspective on sustainability and rank it higher than the price they currently pay for it, their respective behaviour acts as a driver in the wrong direction (Abbasi & Nilsson, 2016).

Given that governments are mostly seen as a necessary, yet not so welcomed driver, combined with the customers that are only slowly starting to act as drivers, what are the barriers the industry is called to overcome?

Firstly, internal operations are still not adequately adapted to meet the expectations needed for a stark change towards sustainability to be structured upon. While our results show a more positive picture on sustainability-reporting than what was indicated by Piecyk & Björklund (2015), international standards for these reports have yet to be established. The studied reports seem to be fundamentally different from one another and the measurements that are shown (if even) are not 100% transparent. There is a severe lack of life cycle measures let alone the fact that simple CO₂ emission scales are not as detailed as they should be given that they are considered 'standard' within the industry to be measured, making the comparison between them unnecessarily harder to explore. Battini et al. (2014) and El Baz and Laguir (2017), among others, have urged LSPs to be more specific about their environmental performance but as we

have concluded from our interviews no one seems to know what that should look like as there is no such protocol to abide by. As a result, there seems to be another miscommunication between academics and practitioners while the miscommunication between management and employees that was found by PwC and APCIS (2014) is interestingly not supported by our findings. Environmental measurements are highly debated but in contrast to what PwC and APCIS (2014) have shown, not knowing the details does not lead to total inaction. Even Company D, a fairly new company and short on knowledge about environmental measurements, is nonetheless reporting on sustainability and has plans for concrete indicators. The three large LSPs are an even better example here. Though the measures are not necessarily clear, their reports are still far-reaching and detailed. Even if parts are purposefully directed to polish the company's image (Wu & Pagell, 2011), they still show the willingness to act on sustainability through their ambitions and projects specifically set to reduce and/or ultimately neutralise their carbon footprint. These three LSPs have defined targets and well-formulated strategies; an approach which has been identified to be of crucial importance on the way to sustainability according to previous research (PwC & APCIS, 2014; El Baz & Laguir, 2017). Secondly, it became clear throughout the interviews that technology is a driver to sustainability. The possibilities given by alternative fuels and new trucks are endless and when and if they are cost-effective in the future with the crucial aid of innovation, these new technologies could pave the path for a greener business. The interviewees were positive that technological advancement would play a major role in the future of logistics, and sustainable logistics in particular, as cheaper, and most importantly, more accessible solutions would become available in the market. However, it is important not to ignore the currently existent scepticism about the practicalities of these technologies as Hofmann and Rüsç (2017) have highlighted. For one, cost-effectiveness is a barrier to initial investment costs (Ding et al., 2016) and secondly, to properly demonstrate the effectiveness of new technologies time will be required that the industry does not have an abundance of.

Thirdly, it seems that the power of influence is a valuable asset in a business field that is highly dependent on partnerships, collaborations, and suppliers to function and operate on a large scale as the LSPs chosen for this study. In the name of market competition, larger LSPs are also perceived as more influential actors in the business setting the standards that the industry currently stands on the matter of sustainability. Crafting contracts with the necessary regulations and compliances is a key factor in determining the level of sustainability within the entirety of the supply chain of the respective LSPs. In other words, the idea of forcing upstream suppliers and downstream partners to sustainability by writing it in their contracts (Oberhofer

& Dieplinger, 2014; Wolf & Seuring, 2010) was adopted by one firm and it seemed to have been constructive giving positive results so far, characterising influence as a driver. For the rest of the large LSPs, it seems that they are in an ongoing process about it but have detected its significance in the way they operate (whilst still underlining the difficulties of such an attempt depending on the country of interest). The medium company admitted that they are unable to take that step yet because of limited alternative options and due to lack of power or influence to do so, thus, for them such a lack is perceived as a barrier.

Lastly, a barrier to the industry's sustainability performance might be the cultural aspect that goes into management practices. El Baz and Laguir (2017), Wolf and Seuring (2010) and Piecky and Björklund (2015) all found the location of LSPs to matter when it comes to sustainability. While our research focus was the European market, one interviewee specifically drew a parallel to the Asian market to describe the difference in culture; in his words, *culture eats strategy for breakfast* (Interviewee #3). The interviewee described it as a form of cultural value that is given to sustainability in Europe and Northern America while others see it more as an optional feature that will be asked for in these markets. This is to show that El Baz and Laguir's (2017) claims are supported by our research; if one market strongly favours sustainability the LSPs headquartered there have leverage over LSPs that want to operate on it. Culture is, therefore, a barrier as long as society does not value sustainability but becomes a driver for outsiders if it becomes a widely recognized merit.

In a nutshell, it can be confirmed that LSPs are taking a rather individual approach in the implementation of environmental sustainability. Driven mostly by outside factors, LSPs have slowly adapted their environmental profile and product offerings in recent years which leads to believe in a sustainable future for the sector. Moreover, the sector seems to have heard of the TBL strategy for most parts, or at least it is aware of the three sustainability dimensions. The concrete steps towards sustainability are, however, yet to be conquered.

6. Conclusions

This study developed around the question *What are the obstacles and drivers multinational LSPs face in their attempt to incorporate sustainability in their business operations?* and the identified results are shown in the model below. The intentions of this paper were not just to name those actors but also to better understand their motivations and relationships to LSPs. As the scale is currently in the cost-effectiveness' favour LSPs are dependent on others to either switch sides or bring new factors into the game. The third option would be to move the tongue of the scale itself (LSPs internal operations & service offerings) but that is certainly more challenging.

Figure 5. Future challenges for LSPs

To achieve environmental sustainability – or Eco-efficiency – in the logistics sector, it seems that LSPs would have to use all their leverage to convince and consequently attract customers over greener logistics while at the same time customers would also have to reevaluate their practices regarding buying decisions and value sustainability more than they used to in the past. The change has been rather slow so far but, as we have demonstrated throughout this research, drivers such as governments and international organisations have begun to incentivise LSPs and customers to switch gears. If these forces are combined and all involved actors strive for more unified and concrete goals, tension in this shearzone might be avoided. At the same time LSPs are struggling with the internal implementation of sustainability – and the corresponding TBL strategy – but there the large LSPs have made a step forward and shown that CSR

reporting and clear communication are possible. Thus, a collaboration – or even keiretsu – between LSPs might also benefit the industry.

One rather uncertain, futuristic factor seems to be the development of sustainable technologies. LSPs are highly dependent on OEMs and R&D to develop greener transport solutions that are also cost-effective, yet only widespread use will make them more affordable which leads to a chicken-egg situation. We, therefore, recommend similarly to (Greschner Farkavcova et al., 2018) for further research to be conducted on the effects technology has on environmental sustainability and economic performance.

Furthermore, this paper highlights the necessity to develop and adapt an effective performance measurement system that assesses the environmental impact of processes, as previous research has also repeatedly encouraged (Colicchia et al., 2013; Wu & Dunn, 1995). This study has taken a qualitative focus to comprehend the underlying structures that LSPs have adopted to address and achieve sustainability but there is an additional necessity within the academic field concerning the subject of green logistics as it is also currently lacking on quantitative studies on the matter. These studies are encouraged as they might also help LSPs to understand cause-effect relations of (in-)action in sustainability.

Moreover, we recommend looking into a longitudinal study design for this industry (Piecyk & Björklund, 2015) that takes a large sample of large-, medium-, and small-sized LSPs to grasp a 360° overview of the industry and the respective relations between LSPs and customers (Wolf & Seuring, 2010).

Concluding this paper, we would like to use a quote from one of our interviewees that sums up the main point of our thesis and gives an overview of the current state of sustainability in the logistics sector while also hinting upon future possibilities:

Let's just say that there is a lot more time spent talking about it compared to the actual impact achieved in the industry. (Interviewee #5)

Reference List

- Abbasi, M., & Nilsson, F. (2016). Developing environmentally sustainable logistics. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, *46*, 273–283. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2016.04.004>
- Armstrong & Associates (2019). *A&A's Top 50 Global Third-Party Logistics Providers (3PLs) List*. Retrieved from: <https://www.3plogistics.com/3pl-market-info-resources/3pl-market-information/aas-top-50-global-third-party-logistics-providers-3pls-list/>
- Battini, D., Persona, A., & Sgarbossa, F. (2014). A sustainable EOQ model: Theoretical formulation and applications. *International Journal of Production Economics*, *149*, 145–153. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2013.06.026>
- Bhaskar, R. (2008). *A Realistic Theory of Science*. Oxon, UK: Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2215817>
- Bolman, L.G. & Deal, T.E. (2013). *Reframing organizations: artistry, choice, and leadership*. (5. ed.) San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Bryman, A. & Bell, E. (2011). *Business Research Methods*. Oxford University Press.
- Burnard, P. (1991). A method of analysing interview transcripts in qualitative research. *Nurse Education Today*, *11*(6), 461–466. [https://doi-org.ezp.sub.su.se/10.1016/0260-6917\(91\)90009-Y](https://doi-org.ezp.sub.su.se/10.1016/0260-6917(91)90009-Y)
- Carey, M., Knowles, C. & Towers-Clark, J. (2017). *Accounting: a smart approach*. (3. ed.) New York, NY: Oxford University Press.
- Centobelli, P., Cerchione, R., & Esposito, E. (2017). Environmental sustainability in the service industry of transportation and logistics service providers: Systematic literature review and research directions. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, *53*, 454–470. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2017.04.032>
- Colicchia, C., Marchet, G., Melacini, M., & Perotti, S. (2013). Building environmental sustainability: Empirical evidence from Logistics Service Providers. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, *59*, 197–209. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2013.06.057>

- Creswell, J.W. (2014). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*. Thousand Oaks: SAGE Publications.
- Ding, H., Liu, Q., & Zheng, L. (2016). Assessing the economic performance of an environmental sustainable supply chain in reducing environmental externalities. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 255(2), 463–480. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2016.05.003>
- Eisenhardt, K. M. (1989). Building Theories from Case Study Research. *Academy of Management Review*, 14(4), 532–550. <https://doi.org/10.5465/AMR.1989.4308385>
- El Baz, J., & Laguir, I. (2017). Third-party logistics providers (TPLs) and environmental sustainability practices in developing countries: The case of Morocco. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 37(10), 1451–1474. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOPM-07-2015-0405>
- Elkington, J. (1997). *Cannibals with forks: The triple bottom line of 21st century business*. Oxford: Capstone.
- Elkington, J. (2014). Enter the Triple Bottom Line. In Henriques, Adrian & Richardson, Julie, *The Triple Bottom Line: Does It All Add Up? : Assessing the Sustainability of Business and CSR*. London: Earthscan.
- Elkington, J. (2018). 25 Years Ago I Coined the Phrase “Triple Bottom Line.” Here’s Why It’s Time to Rethink It. *Harvard Business Review Digital Articles*, 2.
- European Commission. (2011). *White Paper on transport: Roadmap to a single European transport area - Towards a competitive and resource-efficient transport system*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. doi:10.2832/30955
- Eurostat. (2020). *Climate Change - driving forces*. Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Climate_change_-_driving_forces#General_overview
- Evangelista, P. (2014). Environmental sustainability practices in the transport and logistics service industry: An exploratory case study investigation. *Research in Transportation Business & Management*, 12, 63–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rtbm.2014.10.002>

- Evangelista, P., Colicchia, C., & Creazza, A. (2017). Is environmental sustainability a strategic priority for logistics service providers? *Journal of Environmental Management*, *198*, 353–362. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2017.04.096>
- Greschner Farkavcova, V., Rieckhof, R., & Guenther, E. (2018). Expanding knowledge on environmental impacts of transport processes for more sustainable supply chain decisions: A case study using life cycle assessment. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, *61*, 68–83. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2017.04.025>
- Hofmann, E., & Rüsç, M. (2017). Industry 4.0 and the current status as well as future prospects on logistics. *Computers in Industry*, *89*, 23–34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compind.2017.04.002>
- Isaksson, K., & Hüge-Brodin, M. (2013). Understanding efficiencies behind logistics service providers' green offerings. *Management Research Review*, *36*(3), 216–238. <https://doi.org/10.1108/01409171311306382>
- Laari, S., Solakivi, T., Töyli, J., & Ojala, L. (2016). Performance outcomes of environmental collaboration: Evidence from Finnish logistics service providers. *Baltic Journal of Management*, *11*(4), 430–451. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BJM-03-2015-0081>
- Laari, S., Töyli, J., & Ojala, L. (2018). The effect of a competitive strategy and green supply chain management on the financial and environmental performance of logistics service providers. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, *27*(7), 872–883. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2038>
- Lane, B. W. (2019). Revisiting 'An unpopular essay on transportation:' The outcomes of old myths and the implications of new technologies for the sustainability of transport. *Journal of Transport Geography*, *81*, 102535. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2019.102535>
- Lee, K.-H., & Wu, Y. (2014). Integrating sustainability performance measurement into logistics and supply networks: A multi-methodological approach. *The British Accounting Review*, *46*(4), 361–378. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bar.2014.10.005>

- Lieb, K. J., & Lieb, R. C. (2010). Environmental sustainability in the third-party logistics (3PL) industry. *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, 40(7), 524–533. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09600031011071984>
- Maas, S., Schuster, T., & Hartmann, E. (2014). Pollution Prevention and Service Stewardship Strategies in the Third-Party Logistics Industry: Effects on Firm Differentiation and the Moderating Role of Environmental Communication: Pollution Prevention and Service Stewardship in the 3PL Industry. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 23(1), 38–55. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.1759>
- McKinnon, A. C. (eds.). (2015). *Green logistics: Improving the environmental sustainability of logistics*. (3. ed.) London: Kogan Page.
- Moses, J.W. & Knutsen, T.L. (2019). *Ways of knowing: competing methodologies in social and political research*. (3. ed.) London: Red Globe Press.
- Oberhofer, P., & Dieplinger, M. (2014). Sustainability in the Transport and Logistics Sector: Lacking Environmental Measures: Environmental Management in the Transport and Logistics Sector. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 23(4), 236–253. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.1769>
- Piecyk, M. I., & Björklund, M. (2015). Logistics service providers and corporate social responsibility: Sustainability reporting in the logistics industry. *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, 45(5), 459–485. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPDLM-08-2013-0228>
- PwC & APCIS. (2014). *Sustainable Supply Chains: Making Value the Priority*. Retrieved from <https://www.pwc.com/us/en/operations-management/publications/sustainable-supply-chain.jhtml>
- Saglietto, L. (2013). Towards a Classification of Fourth Party Logistics (4PL). *Universal Journal of Industrial and Business Management*, 1(3), 104–116. [https://doi-org.ezp.sub.su.se/http://www.hrpub.org/journals/jour_archive.php?id=16](https://doi.org.ezp.sub.su.se/http://www.hrpub.org/journals/jour_archive.php?id=16)
- Shi, Y., Arthanari, T., Liu, X., & Yang, B. (2019). Sustainable transportation management: Integrated modeling and support. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 212, 1381–1395. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.11.209>

- Smokers, R., Tavasszy, L., Chen, M., & Guis, E. (2014). Options for Competitive and Sustainable Logistics. I C. Macharis, S. Melo, J. Woxenius, & T. V. Lier (eds.), *Transport and Sustainability*, 6, 1-30. Emerald Group Publishing Limited. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S2044-994120140000006001>
- Statista. (2020a). *Size of the freight forwarding market worldwide from 2009 to 2019*. Retrieved from <https://www-statista-com.ezp.sub.su.se/statistics/1066803/freight-forwarding-market-size-worldwide/>
- Statista. (2020b). *Global ocean freight market size from 2017 to 2022*. Retrieved from <https://www-statista-com.ezp.sub.su.se/statistics/983411/global-ocean-freight-market-size/>
- Statista. (2020c). *The world's leading third-party logistics providers in 2018, based on gross logistics revenue*. Retrieved from <https://www-statista-com.ezp.sub.su.se/statistics/250879/leading-third-party-logistics-providers-worldwide-based-on-revenue/>
- Statista. (2020d). *Third-party logistics market size in 2018, by region*. Retrieved from <https://www-statista-com.ezp.sub.su.se/statistics/254875/third-party-logistics-revenue-size-by-region/>
- UNFCCC. (2020). *The Paris Agreement*. Retrieved from <https://unfccc.int/process-and-meetings/the-paris-agreement/the-paris-agreement>
- Welch, C., Piekkari, R., Plakoyiannaki, E. & Paavilainen-Mäntymäki, E. (2011). Theorising from case studies: Towards a pluralist future for international business research. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 42(5), 740–762. <https://doi.org.ezp.sub.su.se/10.1057/jibs.2010.55>
- Wolf, C., & Seuring, S. (2010). Environmental impacts as buying criteria for third party logistical services. *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, 40(1/2), 84–102. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09600031011020377>
- Wu, H., & Dunn, S. C. (1995). Environmentally responsible logistics systems. *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, 25(2), 20–38. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09600039510083925>

Wu, Z., & Pagell, M. (2011). Balancing priorities: Decision-making in sustainable supply chain management. *Journal of Operations Management*, 29(6), 577–590. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jom.2010.10.001>

Yang, C.-S., Lu, C.-S., Haider, J. J., & Marlow, P. B. (2013). The effect of green supply chain management on green performance and firm competitiveness in the context of container shipping in Taiwan. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review*, 55, 55–73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tre.2013.03.005>

Appendix

Interview Guide

1. The Interviewee
 - a. What is your role?
 - b. How long have you been in the business? And in this company?

2. Sustainability in general
 - a. How would you define sustainability?
 - b. How would you describe the role of sustainability in today's world?

3. Sustainability in the logistics sector
 - a. What do you think are the most important sustainability trends in the logistics sector?
 - b. How would you describe the role of sustainability in the logistics sector today compared to 20 years ago?

4. LSPs' role in the Supply Chain
 - a. From your experience what role would you say do LSPs have in the Supply Chain (compared for example to the customers)?
 - b. How much influence does the rest of the Supply Chain have on the operations of LSPs? And which parts are the most affected?
 - c. How do outsiders influence the industry? For example, the government, NGOs, etc.

5. External Collaborations
 - a. Is there some form of collaborations among LSPs? Do you outsource? If yes, why? How does it affect your sustainability reporting? Do these collaborations contribute to improved sustainability or do they hinder it? Why?
 - b. How do partnerships/collaborations between LSPs and customers look like when it comes to sustainability? Which role do such partnerships play?

6. Internal Processes

- a. What does your company do for sustainability? What is your business strategy? Does it incorporate sustainability?
- b. How does your company make money because of/in spite of sustainability?
- c. Where do you focus your sustainability efforts? Is it product development, transport optimization, service operations, marketing, etc.?
- d. What was the motivator for your company to pursue sustainability efforts?
- e. Which role does sustainability play in your personal day-to-day practices? And which role does it play in the company's day-to-day practices?
- f. How does your company measure sustainability? How do you measure economic performance? Do you compare those two measures?
- g. How does internal collaboration among departments look like when it comes to sustainability?
- h. What are the dilemmas, trade-offs that you and your colleagues face in terms of sustainability?
- i. Internally speaking do you believe that there is a balance between environmental sustainability and economic performance or is one favoured over the other? Why?

Comments: Do you have any questions? Anything you would like to add/ expand on?

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